
New data model for logistics in furniture B2B collaborations

1.1. Introduction

In March 2018 AIDIMME held a workshop to perform an initial validation of NIMBLE B2B platform (H2020 European funded project NIMBLE - GA No 723810). In that workshop participated furniture manufacturers and experts in the logistics field, and they tested the next services of the platform: publish catalog of the product (furniture) and services (logistics), search for products/services and negotiate.

The logistics testing team involved in that workshop pointed it was difficult to publish their logistics services with the ontologies the platform offers at that moment: furniture ontology and eClass.

They found a lack of concepts and terminology which does not allow them to publish all the main characteristics of their logistics services. On one hand, the furniture ontology was well detailed on furniture products but not on logistics services. On the other hand, eClass was extremely detailed but the users found quite difficult to deal with the different levels and topics of this ontology. Indeed, they found also a gap between this ontology and some properties of their services because of the customization of the logistics services they can offer to the furniture companies. To overcome these problems in NIMBLE platform it was developed a new logistics ontology based on a new data model for logistics services in the furniture sector. In this paper, it is explained the main structure and characteristics of this ontology and its performance after a new validation round with experts in logistics.

1.2. Overview of existing data models

Ontologies enable common understanding of concepts and have been acknowledged as a powerful means to foster collaboration between companies [DAN 13]. Although numerous ontologies for production systems have been developed in the past years, they mainly focus on manufacturing, while logistics have not received the same attention [NEG 17]. It is certain there are studies about this problem [LEU 08], [SCH 12], [ZYG 10], [DAN 13], [NEG 17], but the problem to fit logistics processes and ontologies continues.

In some models there is a lack of formal semantics which prevents automated data integration across organizational boundaries [LEU 08], and it is difficult to balance the trade-off between precision and pragmatism in a logistics ontology [DAN 13]

eClass is one of the most prominent product classification standards covering a wide range of products and services and grows continuously [HEP 05]. It contains thousands of product/service categories and associated properties. The eClass taxonomy were limited in utilization of the NIMBLE use case in terms of both the available categories and properties associated to those properties in relation to logistics services. For instance, eClass does not include classification categories representing warehouse management or reverse logistics. Furthermore, for some other logistics services like rail or road transport, though, eClass has representative categories but with insufficient properties to represent details about those categories in the scope of NIMBLE use case.

Apart from eClass, there exists several product classification standards for classification of products/services. Global Product Classification (GPC) [GS1 20], Google Product Taxonomy [GOG 20] and UNSPSC[XU 12] are some of the product classification standards. However, they are also not suitable to address problems explained above. Schulten et al. (2001) indicates that UNSPSC is rather shallow, not very intuitive, and not descriptive on an attribute level and it is mainly developed in the US, leaving many European needs behind [SCH 01]. Whereas Google Product Taxonomy does not define a category for any type of logistics services, GPC defines a category only for general transport services.

Neither eClass nor other product classification standards are enough to ease the process of publishing/discovering of logistics services in furniture sector. Therefore, we define a furniture logistics ontology for different types of logistics services having some common properties such as industry specialization and specific properties to the service such as truck load property for road transport.

1.2. Experimentation methodology

The work was performed in different steps during the continuous user validation carried out in NIMBLE platform (<https://www.nimble-project.org/project/furniture-manufacturing-platform/>). The problem with the current ontologies available in NIMBLE arised after the first user validation steps described in the introduction.

Figure N.1. Work methodology.

Firstly, it was defined a new logistics services data model, specifically suitable for the logistics operations of the furniture arena. The inputs of the previous workshops and questionnaires were taking into account, but it was necessary to have face to face interviews with logistics companies and furniture manufacturers in order to pick up their requirements. Once the new data model was ready, it was integrated into the Furniture sector ontology and adapted to NIMBLE requirements.

After these steps, it was planned a new user validation workshop with some logistics experts in the furniture sector. It was prepared a detailed and personalized agenda with the experimentation of each participant, indicating: (i) the role of the participant at each stage of the experimentation (buyer, supplier, manufacturer, logistics, retailer), (ii) the company and products to be registered, (iii) the searches to be performed on the platform and (iv) the negotiation pairs between participants during the workshop.

Every participant in the workshop tested all the functionalities running available on the NIMBLE platform (related to the different business processes): (i) register a member on the platform, (ii) register a company on the platform by using the previous member account, (iii) publish some logistics services, (iv) search logistics services, filtering by parameters and comparing retrieved items and (v) negotiate with suppliers or potential customers for these services.

The logistics services used as a testing service covered different parts of the furniture supply chain: transport, warehousing and packaging. Once the platform had been extensively experimented, users took part in open discussions and filled questionnaires for further evaluation.

1.3. Logistics data model for logistics in the furniture sector.

1.3.1. Brief description of the ontology for logistics services

The logistics data model, was integrated in the Furniture Sector Ontology, based on the International standard for the information exchange FunStep (ISO 10303-236) [FUN] focused on wood and furniture-related items. This means a common vocabulary and includes the most used concepts and properties in the furniture sector industry as well as its main relationships. This is implemented in OWL and it is based on the knowledge of AIDIMME from the experts as well as furniture cluster regulations, articles and interviews. The ontology covers the following main resources in the furniture industry: furniture products and services, manufacturing processes and techniques, industrial machines, equipment and facilities.

All the elements included in the ontology are annotated with labels in English and Spanish languages. These translations are consumed by the NIMBLE frontend to render all the categories and properties in the UI according to the language selected by the user. Furthermore, many concepts are annotated with RDF comments in both languages to make a clear description available to the users.

1.3.2. Logistics data model as an ontology extension

The data model for the representation of logistics services was preliminary defined based on graphical user interfaces provided by logistics experts. These mockups enabled the elicitation of service categories as well as its properties and a corresponding tentative rank of values for some of these properties. All these resources were integrated in the furniture sector ontology as an extension. The picture below illustrates an excerpt of the categorization of logistics services which was defined from the mockups proposed by users.

Figure N.3. Detail of logistics services defined as an extension of the Furniture Sector Ontology.

1.3.3. Integration with NIMBLE platform (ontology annotations)

In order to achieve a full compatibility between the properties defined in the ontology and the data model used by NIMBLE, additional annotations were included in the ontology. Therefore, the ontology manages two main annotations for the NIMBLE integration: QuantityType (for the representation of measuring units for properties such as dimensions or weight) and CodeType (for the representation of values for properties which do not have a numerical range).

Figure N.4. Detail of representation of property values of logistics services in the furniture sector ontology.

The representation of a truck load service can be taken as an example. The truck load is a kind of road transport service and is represented as an object property. This property may take three different values (full, partial and groupage truck loads). All these elements have their own code. They are modelled as individuals and wrapped in a code list (TruckLoadList).

1.3.4. User interface for logistics publication

The preliminary mockups together with the formal data model were taken as reference to build a user-friendly frontend to enable the publication of comprehensive logistics services by specialized companies. The publication of logistics services is organized in seven tabs: transport (road, maritime, air and rail), warehousing, order picking, reverse logistics, in-house services, customs management and logistics consultancy. Each service allows a particular indication of the origin and destination capabilities, as well as text descriptions and file attachments to clarify any aspect regarding the service provided by the company.

1.4. Results and lessons learnt.

The new logistics services data model saves time in the publishing and negotiation services in the NIMBLE platform instance for furniture and related industries. Being more specific, these are the specific main benefits: (i) when a company offers global services, they can publish quickly some generic logistics services, and in a specific request or negotiation, they can specify more their

conditions, (ii) the logistics companies who offer customized services can publish simple standard services without any complexity, but specify details later during the negotiation process, (iii) the meaning of the properties is clear enough for users, therefore the time needed to publish services is reduced and (iv) the number of properties is suitable for the most common logistics services in the furniture industry.

It can be stated that a formalized testing agenda based on open discussion, feedback from questionnaires and live experimentation with user guidelines and technical support at workshops, is crucial to reveal undiscovered requirements

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